

Consultation European Commission for the Forthcoming Data Union Strategy. Views of the DATAMITE Consortium.

THE CURRENT & THE FORTHCOMING DATA UNION STRATEGY

The current European Strategy for Data contributes towards the creation of a single market for data that ensures global competitiveness and data sovereignty for Europe, thereby also leading to the creation of Common European Data Spaces. Consequently, vast amount of data is constantly becoming available for use in the economy and society, while also keeping companies and individuals generating the data in control. To further safeguard EU's role as a leader in the global data economy, the Strategy is particularly concentrated on: adopting legislative measures on data governance, access and reuse (e.g., for business-to-government data sharing for the public interest); making data more widely accessible through the opening up of high-value publicly held datasets across the EU, allowing their reuse for free; investing billions of euros in a European High Impact Project to develop data processing infrastructures, data sharing tools, architectures and governance mechanisms enabling data sharing and federating energy-efficient and trustworthy cloud infrastructures and related services; enabling access to secure, fair and competitive cloud services by facilitating the set-up of a procurement marketplace for data processing services.

In view of the launched Open Consultation on the forthcoming New European Strategy for Data, the following paragraphs are concerned with evaluating considerations drawn from the experience of DATAMITE, but also general views beyond its context, that shall serve as guiding points when deciding on the pillars of the New Strategy.

THE DATAMITE PROJECT IN SHORT

DATAMITE is a project funded by the European Commission as part of the Horizon Europe programme and coordinated by the ITI – Technological Institute of Informatics. DATAMITE empowers European companies by delivering a modular, open-source and multi-domain Framework to improve DATA Monetizing, Interoperability, Trading and Exchange, in the form of software modules, training, and business materials.

DATAMITE unleashes the monetisation potential at two levels. At internal level, users shall have tools to improve quality management of their data, the adherence to

FAIR principles, and is going to be able to upskill on technical and business aspects thanks to the multiple open-source training materials the project generates. Therefore, data shall become trustable and more reliable also in other paradigms like AI.

At external level, keeping users in control of their data shall provide new sources of revenue and interaction with other stakeholders. The architecture envisioned for DATAMITE enables DIHs sandboxing, becoming a potential instructor on their onboarding of SMEs and low-tech SMEs into the data economy. Together, DATAMITE's solutions shall function as a catalyst to boost data monetisation in the European productive fabric.

DATAMITE Use Cases (UCs) differentiate in two key parts, **how data is treated and how data is shared**. In all UCs, **data governance, quality or security modules** are used, thereby aiming at improving how data is managed within companies, how good data is, as well as how interoperable data is across organisational boundaries. The six core pilots are as follows: Corporate Multi-Domain Data Exchange with DIH Support (represented by GIDITEK, ITI, EGI); Corporate Multi-Site Data Exchange (represented by OTE, EGI); Offering Data to Service Providers with Dataspaces (represented by HEDNO, CERTH); Leveraging Electricity Distribution Open Data (represented by E-REDES); Connecting EDWIN to Data Markets (represented by WODR, PSNC, AGREGO); Connecting Mistral to the EU AI-ON-DEMAND Platform (represented by CINECA, UCC).

THOUGHTS ON INTEROPERABILITY AND THE EC'S PROPOSED THREE PILLARS – THE PERSPECTIVE OF DATAMITE

First and foremost, **Enhancing Cross-Sectoral and Intra-Sectoral European Data Spaces' Interoperability** shall be prioritized and promoted by the forthcoming Data Strategy. More particularly, DATAMITE proposes to the European Commission (hereinafter "EC") to prioritise the development of a common, harmonised approach, as a prerequisite to leverage the data spaces development, thereby also allowing for the evolution of sectoral regulations, **similarly to the existing model in the health sector**. Taking the energy sector as a use case exemplifying the discussed need, based on the tests performed between DATAMITE and the existing energy data spaces, the following conclusions have been drawn.

Firstly, **lack of technical and semantic interoperability persists** due to divergent functional architecture models, namely, in relation to **incorporation of the GAIA-X, IDS and Data Spaces Protocol requisites in the architectures**. Due to the divergent technology implementations across different energy data spaces, the potential for convergence and cross-border collaboration is thus being undermined.

Consequently, it shall be acknowledged that without a common framework and shared standards, there is a risk of deepening the silos rather than bridging them. Therefore, it is **essential that all sectoral data spaces are built with interoperability at their core, guided by a shared European reference architecture**. Furthermore, **user involvement and co-creation** are critical for ensuring that data spaces remain adaptive, inclusive, and fit for purpose in a rapidly evolving digital landscape.

DATAMITE thus recommends that the **EC adopts a coordinated, horizontal strategy, to enable the technical, semantic, and legal interoperability of data spaces from the outset**, thereby unlocking the full value of data for all sectors and citizens.

As the EC is proposing to base the forthcoming Data Union Strategy on the below-referenced three main pillars, the same are discussed from the point of experience within DATAMITE.

I) Improving and Facilitating Secure Private and Public Data Sharing

To enhance private and public data sharing at European level, the following points for action must be addressed:

- **Clear data governance frameworks** that define roles, responsibilities, and access rights for all stakeholders.
- **Interoperability-by-design** through common standards and reference architectures, developed collaboratively but flexibly recognising national and regional specificities.
- **Support for secure, value-driven data exchange**, including mechanisms for trusted anonymisation and cybersecurity.
- In a **check & balances** manner, data spaces themselves, and not only technology providers, shall be responsible for ensuring/certifying that participants share data in a legally and ethically compliant manner.
- **Common Data Monetization Framework EU-wide is needed, including further unification towards a common EU-wide regulatory approach.**

II) Simplifying the Regulatory Regime, Improving Consistency, and Fostering Application

To enhance the stance of the existing regulatory framework, the following must be ensured:

- **Light-touch, principle-based regulation**, focused on key outcomes like transparency, accountability, and interoperability.
- **Promote and develop regulatory sandboxes** and pilot-friendly frameworks that allow different stakeholders to test data-sharing models in real conditions before scaling.
- **Soft law instruments**, e.g.: guidelines; codes of conduct; or common reference architectures – co-created with the sector and updated iteratively. Ready-to-use templates for organisations, elaborating on and harmonising the efforts at national level, shall also be encouraged, as well as the creation of straightforward and easy

to apply resources, including checklists, practical guidelines for compliance in action, etc.

- **Measures for enhancing consistency of the application and enforcement by national authorities**, e.g.: collection of positions by national authorities on priority issues taken in national guidance and decisions, including court judgements, thus producing publications in a “case law” manner, thereby assisting organisations in understanding concrete positions taken concerning interpretation; ongoing monitoring to further complement guidelines, to ensure effectiveness and consistent application including through reviews of the same, as well as through targeted coordinated enforcement actions and strategies; continued effort in aligning domestic and EU-level guidance in cases of identified inconsistencies; develop common practices, methodologies, tools and common actions for greater harmonisation of enforcement.
- **Cross-Regulatory Measures to Improve Consistency**, e.g.: preparing joint guidelines together with regulators, as deemed appropriate, in order to ensure consistency in the application of different legal frameworks; enabling effective and structured cooperation amongst regulators to exchange experience and to address legal and practical challenges in cross-regulatory cooperation on concrete cases; fostering proactively meetings between domestic regulators and relevant EU bodies, as deemed relevant.

The above-referenced measures shall reduce the overall complexity of regulations, currently constituting more of a hurdle for smaller actors in terms of ensuring compliance, as usually only big companies have in-house lawyers. As many SMEs do not understand or are oftentimes not even aware of legal & ethics requirements, this shall thus enable all stakeholders, including SMEs, to identify their obligations and ensure compliance. On the other hand, the proposed measures shall also improve overall consistency, application, as well as enforcement of the regulatory framework.

III) Accelerating the Development of New Systems and Applications

To enhance systems and applications development at the European level, the following must be ensured:

- **Avoid mandates** of specific platforms or architectures which risk locking stakeholders into rigid or costly solutions.
- **Support reference frameworks** that allow diverse systems to interconnect, rather than replace what works locally.
- **Encourage the development of open APIs**, common data models, and shared ontologies which make it easier to build interoperable apps and services.

CONCLUDING REMARKS

All in all, as has been observed further actions concerning the stance of interoperability are needed. In addition, clear data governance frameworks, support for secure and value-driven data exchange, as well as Common Data Monetization Standards EU-Wide, are awaiting to be addressed. Of course, overall simplification of the regulatory regime, improving consistency, and fostering application, are all steps of an imperative importance, too. Finally, enhancing systems and applications development at the European level, the following must be ensured: avoid mandates of specific platforms or architectures which may lead to locking stakeholders into rigid or costly solutions; encourage reference frameworks that allow diverse systems to interconnect, instead of replacing what works locally; and, encourage support the development of open APIs, common data models, as well as shared ontologies which make it easier to build interoperable apps and services.

Started in January 2023, DATAMITE is an initiative funded by the European Union's Horizon Europe Research and Innovation programme under grant agreement N° 101092989, with a strong focus on data monetising, interoperability, trading and exchange.